

Cardiorenal Syndrome in Heart Failure Patients: A Descriptive and Predictive Study

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Abstract:

Aim & Objectives: This study aims to evaluate the prevalence, contributing causes, and consequences of Cardiorenal syndrome (CRS) in patients with heart failure (HF) admitted to medical wards of a tertiary care hospital.

Material & Methods: The research employed a cross-sectional design. During a 15-month period, patients who met the specific requirements and were at least 18 years old were recruited individually. In addition to the essential first blood tests, such as blood profile, CBC, urine analysis, eGFR, ECG, echocardiography, and renal USG, a comprehensive medical history and physical examination were conducted. The urine protein creatinine ratio was evaluated in individuals with proteinuria. At the initial presentation, serum creatinine, urea, and electrolyte levels were assessed. Subsequently, over the course of heart failure therapy, identical measurements were repeated. The precise description and categorization of heart failure and CRS were achieved utilising acceptable criteria. Statistical analysis conducted with the SPSS programme.

Results: Out of the 100 patients examined, the average age was 50.639±13.401, with 62 being men and 38 being females. Out of the total, 53 individuals had cardiorenal impairment, whereas 47 individuals were exclusively in the heart failure patient group. The CRS group, including 86.8% of the participants, consists of individuals aged 40 and above (p=0.0401) who have a high prevalence of diabetes. In contrast, the non-CRS group, accounting for 76% of the participants, does not smoke. The majority of individuals impacted suffer from type 1 CRS, and 72.5% of CRS cases are classified as moderate CRS. High levels of serum urea (>120 mg/dl) and serum creatinine (>1.91 mg/dl) can be used to predict mortality. Individuals diagnosed with CRS exhibited significantly greater mortality rates compared to those who did not have the illness.

Conclusion: Patients with heart failure exhibited markedly elevated rates of CRS. Individuals who were beyond the age of 40 and classified as NYHA class 4 were found to be independent predictors of CRS. Individuals with chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS) had significantly prolonged hospital stays compared to individuals without CRS. Within a hospital setting, the death rate for individuals with CRS is significantly elevated. Serum urea and creatinine serve as crucial indicators of mortality.

Keywords: Cardiorenal syndrome; CRS; Creatinine; GFR; HF; Urea.

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Introduction

Heart failure (HF) is becoming identified as a global public health concern that affects countries with diverse economic backgrounds. Health system crises can arise in areas with low resources due to the substantial burden of high rates of heart failure and the need for therapies that demand a lot of money. [1] Based on the INDUS survey, the prevalence of the disease in India is estimated to be at 1.2 instances per 1000 individuals. The one-year death rate for people with chronic heart failure is 7.2%, while the one-year hospitalisation rate is 31.9% following the onset of the condition.

Nevertheless, the percentages rise to 17.4% and 43.9%, respectively, for persons admitted to the hospital due to acute heart failure. The global prevalence of heart failure has surpassed 23 million individuals. [2] Cardiorenal syndrome (CRS) is a medical condition that leads to sudden or long-term impairments in the functioning of both the heart and kidneys, resulting in dysfunctions in another organ. Variations in pro-inflammatory molecular patterns and neuro-hormonal markers unique to its clinical features, as well as the dynamics of blood flow between the failing heart and the kidneys and

vice versa. [3] The development of cardiorenal syndrome is connected with the sympathetic nervous system, inflammation, changes in the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS), and an imbalance between nitric oxide (NO) and reactive oxygen species (ROS). These parts serve as the connections that link the renal and cardiovascular systems.[2] Heart failure leads to a drop in renal perfusion pressure, resulting in the constriction of the afferent arterioles that deliver blood to the kidneys. Consequently, the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) and renal blood flow experience further decline.

Heart failure (HF) has more severe repercussions due to the increased frequency of catecholamine release and less elimination. [4] Patients suffering from heart failure (HF) often encounter renal impairment (RI), and around 20% to 40% of patients admitted to hospitals for acute heart failure syndromes (AHFS) often exhibit concurrent renal impairment (RI). [5] Renal impairment, characterised by a rise in serum creatinine of at least 25% or levels equivalent to or exceeding 2 mg/dl, was previously observed to be prevalent among patients having aggressive therapy for heart failure.[6] Patients with progressive renal failure are increasingly recognising cardiovascular issues as the primary cause of death.[7] The coexistence of renal diseases and heart failure is increasingly acknowledged as separate risk factors that contribute to the development of illness and death.[8] The care of individuals with heart failure and the prediction of their prognosis are greatly influenced by the combination of each of these factors. [9] Even a slight decline in kidney function, as shown by an elevation in blood creatinine or a reduction in estimated glomerular filtration rate (GFR), significantly increases the likelihood of developing cardiovascular disease.[10] Research indicates that there is a direct correlation between a decrease of 1 ml/min in creatinine clearance and a corresponding rise of 1% in patient mortality. Moreover, those who have a slight decrease in renal function face an equivalent cardiovascular risk to individuals with diabetes mellitus. [11,12]

Irrespective of conventional measures of heart failure severity, renal insufficiency is linked to adverse outcomes and serves as both an indication of advanced cardiac disease and a direct contributor to illness and death in individuals with HF. Research has indicated that individuals who are admitted to the hospital with acute heart failure syndrome (AHFS) have higher chances of illness and death if they already have pre-existing kidney dysfunction (RI). [5-15] An thorough study of data from 1,129 patients revealed that the most significant independent predictor of readmission for any reason was a blood creatinine level over 2.5

mg/dL at the time of discharge. [5,16] Using data from 541 people, a multivariate Cox regression analysis was performed. The results showed a strong correlation between all-cause mortality and rising quartiles of xv Blood urea nitrogen (BUN) levels. [5,17] Patients with both renal dysfunction and left ventricular systolic dysfunction (LVSD) were more likely to have more severe heart failure symptoms than patients with normal renal function and LVSD, as shown by their higher NYHA Class, according to an analysis of data from the SOLVD study. [19] A study conducted by HR Shah et al. examined the clinical characteristics and outcomes of individuals with CRS in North India. Consequently, there is limited knowledge on the occurrence of different types of CRS, the variables that impact them, their impact on health and death rates in Central India, and the factors that contribute to them. Furthermore, rural primary care physicians are faced with the task of managing a growing prevalence of cardiovascular disorders, which can lead to heart failure and renal complications.[4,9] This study was aimed to ascertain the prevalence, classifications, and results (i.e., duration of hospital stay and death) of people with CRS. Additionally, the goal is to identify the risk factors associated with death in people with CRS. The incidence and death rates linked to CRS can be lowered by promptly identifying certain risk factors.

Aims and Objectives:

1. The study's goals included determining the prevalence and effects of CRS in patients with heart failure (HF) who were admitted to the outpatient facility, as well as the following: The aim of this study is to determine the features that may suggest and causally contribute to the development of CRS in patients admitted to hospitals due to heart failure (HF).
2. The objective is to assess the length of hospitalisation and mortality rate among patients with CRS who are hospitalised for heart failure (HF). The study also aims to identify the determinants of mortality in individuals with CRS who are admitted to the hospital due to heart failure.

Materials and Methods:

The study was carried out at the medical department of a hospital affiliated with a medical college. The study design is cross-sectional. The study included patients who satisfied the Framingham criteria for heart failure and were admitted to the hospital for a minimum of 18 years. The study excluded individuals who declined to provide permission for participation in the trial and who were already receiving regular dialysis therapy before enrolment. The research was authorised by the institutional Ethical Committee, and each

patient gave informed permission. The Helsinki declaration was followed. Patients who met the criteria were sequentially included until the desired sample size was reached. A structured questionnaire was utilised to inquire individuals who were suspected of having heart failure regarding their clinical history, anthropometric measures, general and cardiovascular tests, and demographic information. The patients had diagnostic tests including serum creatinine [SCr], urea coupled with electrolytes, blood sugar levels, serum uric acid, blood lipid levels, urine analysis, electrocardiogram (ECG), and echocardiography. When an individual's urine analysis reveals the presence of protein, the urinary protein-creatinine ratio is computed to quantify the amount of protein excreted in a 24-hour urine sample.

Each individual underwent a renal ultrasound examination. The Cockcroft-Gault equation, which has undergone thorough testing and has been proven to be a reliable method, was used to predict the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) of Indian patients. [20-22] At the conclusion of the therapy or on the seventh day, the levels of serum creatinine, urea, and electrolytes were assessed. The revised Framingham Criteria were employed to establish the diagnosis of heart failure. [23] A diagnostic criterion for renal impairment in heart failure (cardiorenal syndrome) is an estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) below 60 ml/min/1.73 m². [4,9] The severity of clinical symptoms was evaluated using the New York Heart Association (NYHA) functional class. [20]

Methodology:

A conventional mercury sphygmomanometer was employed to assess the blood pressure in both the left and right arms. The arm with the highest recorded blood pressure was tested and recorded. The weight was quantified in kilogrammes using a weight-based scale equipped with twelve lead surfaces, while the height was measured in metres using a stadiometer. An electrocardiogram (ECG) was used to record the heart's electrical activity. The investigator utilised ECG equipment to

document the physiological data of each recruited individual. The researcher conducted transthoracic echocardiography for every patient. The measurements were conducted using the leading-edge to leading-edge convention and simultaneous ECG recording, following the guidelines provided by the American Society of Echocardiography (ASE). [19] A signal or transmission that remains uninterrupted and maintains a consistent flow is known as continuous-wave.

The Doppler approach was employed to investigate the valves when the presence of a valvular abnormality was suspected. Tissue Doppler imaging was employed to distinguish between normal and pseudo-normal left ventricular filling in individuals with diastolic dysfunction. White blood cell counts and haemoglobin measurement were conducted using an EDTA blood collection container. After an overnight fast of 8-12 hours, a sample of venous blood measuring 10 ml was collected to assess the levels of lipids (triglycerides, total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein, HDL, and LDL) as well as fasting blood sugar (FBS). A mechanised analyzer was employed to quantify the levels of creatinine, urea, and electrolytes in the serum. The central lab analysed all of the samples.

Data Analysis:

The gathered data was constructed, verified, and analysed using version 16.0 of the computerised statistical software package for social sciences, often known as SPSS. The mean and standard deviation were used to characterise quantitative variables. Statistical significance was determined as a P value below 0.05.

Observation and Results:

A total of one hundred patients who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were assessed. Their gender distribution was a male to female ratio of 1.6 to 1, with 62 men accounting for 62% and 38 females accounting for 38%. The age of the patients varied from 18 to 90 years, with an average age of 50.639 ± 13.401.

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of patients

Variables	N
Age (years)	50.639±13.401
Gender Male	62
Female	38
Hypertension	57
Diabetes	49
Dyslipidemia	46
Smoking	37
Alcoholic	39
Hypothyroidism	16
Systolic dysfunction	51
Diastolic dysfunction	49

Clinical aetiology of HF	Hypertensive heart disease	37
	Dilated cardiomyopathy	35
	Peripartum cardiomyopathy	10
	Rheumatic heart disease	10
	Ischemic heart disease	2
	Cor-pulmonale	3
Systolic blood pressure (SBP) (mm Hg)		127.611±33.038
Diastolic blood pressure (DBP) (mm Hg)		74.728±10.892
Haemoglobin (Hb) (mg/dl)		10.458±1.902
Serum urea (mg/dl)		50.712±24.792
Serum creatinine (mg/dl)		2.102±3.098
eGFR (ml/min)		59.352±33.302
Total cholesterol (TC) (mg/dl)		193.789±57.792
Left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) (%)		44.889±11.802

Majority of patients have dyspnoea of grade 4. Compared to the group without CRS, those with CRS, 86.8% were above 40 years (86.8% vs. 69.6% p <0.04), had higher frequency diabetes (62.3% vs. 34.8% p= 0.0092) (Table-2).

Table 2: Comparison of the clinical characteristics and echocardiographic findings among the patients

Variables	Total n=100	CRS present n=53	CRS absent n=47	P-value
Gender-Male	62	37	25	0.1471
Female	38	16	22	
Age(years)	50.639±13.401	53.512±13.592	47.328±12.588	0.0212
BMI	23.088±2.602	23.278±2.202	22.878±3.022	0.4491
Hypertension	57	34	23	0.2191
Diabetes	49	33	16	0.0092
Paroxysmal nocturnal dyspnoea (PND)	81	50	31	0.0012
Orthopnoea	80	50	30	0.0012
Jugular venous pressure (JVP)	76	45	31	0.0438
Cardiomegaly	83	49	34	0.0102
Third heart sound (S3)	75	47	28	0.0012
Systolic Dysfunction (SD)	51	24	27	0.3702
Diastolic Dysfunction (DD)	58	34	24	0.4489
LVEF <50	72	37	35	0.3379

Within the CRS group, 9.3% achieved severe grades, 18.5% obtained moderate marks, and 72.2% received mild ratings. The majority of individuals suffering from the illness consisted of 41 people (77.35%) who were diagnosed with CRS. Out of the whole sample, eight individuals (15.09%) were diagnosed with type II CRS, while the remaining four patients (7.5%) were diagnosed with type IV CRS. None of the research individuals had Type III or V CRS.

Figure 1: CLASSIFICATION OF CRS AMONG THE GROUP

CRS classification within the CRS group is shown in Figure -1. Severe: HF+eGFR <15mL/min/1.73m² or dialysis; mild: HF+eGFR 30-59mL/min/1.73m², moderate: HF+eGFR 15-29mL/min/1.73m²,

The CRS 2 group had substantially higher mean serum urea levels (59.51 mg/dl vs. 39.61 mg/dl, $p < 0.00011$) and creatinine levels (3.13 mg/dl vs. 1.01 mg/dl, $p < 0.00011$) compared to the group

without CRS. However, according to Table 3, the average eGFR in the CRS group was significantly lower (34.99 ml/min compared to 87.40 ml/min, $p < 0.00011$). Out of the individuals involved in the study, 75 individuals or 75% exhibited proteinuria.

Out of all the patients, 33.33% of those without CRS had proteinuria, whereas 66.66% of those with proteinuria had CRS. The p-value of 0.0171 indicates a statistically significant difference.

Table 3: Comparison of the laboratory parameters among patients with & without CRS

Variables	CRS present	CRS absent	P-value
	Mean±SD	Mean±SD	
Hb (mg/dL)	10.325±1.742	10.615±2.102	0.4552
Total cholesterol (mg/dl)	191.682±64.128	196.142±50.088	0.7028
eGFR (ml/min)	34.988±11.982	87.403±27.362	<0.00011
Urea (mg/dl)	59.512±26.448	39.612±17.683	<0.00011
SCr (mg/dl)	3.132±3.748	1.013±1.232	<0.00011

Table 4: Comparison of clinical variables among patients with and without cardiorenal syndrome

Variables	CRS present	CRS absent	P-value
	n=53	n=47	
Age (>40years)	46	32	0.0402
SBP >160mmHg	15	5	0.0398
Diabetes	33	16	0.0088
NYHA IV	33	15	0.0082
Anaemia	24	17	0.4212

Table 5: Mortality and duration of hospital stay

Variables	Total patients	CRS present	CRS absent	P-value
	n=100	n=53	n=47	
Death	35	31	4	<0.00011
Duration of stay (days)	9.412±7.088	10.418±3.702	8.258±9.512	<0.00011

The patient outcomes (death and length of hospital stay) are displayed in Table 5. 35 (35%) of the 100 participants passed away. 31 people (58.5%) in the CRS group and 4 people (8.7%) in the non-CRS group passed away (p value <0.00011), indicating a considerably greater death rate in the CRS group. The CRS group's mean hospital stay lasted 10.418 ± 3.702 days, while the non-CRS group's mean stay was 8.258 ± 9.512 days (P value <0.00011). A comparison of the results for the CRS and non-CRS groups.

Table 6: Comparison of Deceased and Survivors of CRS

Variables	Deceased	Survivors	P-value
	n=31	n=22	
NYHA class IV (%)	20 (64.51)	11 (50)	0.0092
DM	722.8	418.18	0.9011
SBP <160mmHg	15 (48.38)	18 (90.6)	0.0011
DBP <60mmHg	4 (11.4)	10 (15.6)	0.7589
SCr >1.91mg/dl	20 (64.51)	10 (45.45)	0.0012
Urea >120mg/dl	13 (41.93)	5 (22.72)	0.0012
eGFR <53ml/min	31 (100)	19 (86.36)	0.0448
Cholesterol >200mg/dl	14 (40.0%)	28 (43.8)	0.8302

Table 6 presents a comparison of laboratory and clinical findings between survivors and non-survivors of CRS.

Patients who had serum creatinine (SCr) levels equal to or greater than 1.91 mg/dl, urea levels higher than 120 mg/dl, estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) levels lower than 53 ml/min, and were classified as NYHA class IV had a

substantially increased percentage of deaths ($p=0.0012$, 0.0012 , 0.0448 , and 0.0092 , respectively). On the other hand, a higher percentage of survivors had systolic blood pressure (SBP) levels below 160 mmHg ($p=0.0011$) compared to non-survivors.

Discussion

53.5% of the research participants displayed the condition. The prevalence rate of the current study is slightly higher than the rates reported in previous local research studies on the incidence of kidney damage in patients with heart failure. [7,8] The research uncovered a high occurrence of renal damage in individuals undergoing treatment for heart failure, with rates ranging from 7% to 50%. The incongruous outcomes might be ascribed to discrepancies in the research methods and the demographic traits of the study participants. However, several prior studies have shown that CRS commonly occurs. [22-24] Research findings suggest that 60% of individuals diagnosed with acute decompensate heart failure (ADHF) had a moderate level of cardiorenal syndrome (CRS). [24] The mean age of the participants in this study was 50.639 ± 13.401 years, which may be regarded as rather youthful. This discovery is consistent with the results of a previous inquiry carried out on persons suffering from heart failure at the research site, as well as another study with patients from western Odisha, located in the western region of Nigeria. The mean age of participants in both trials was 45.531 ± 8.611 years. [7] Nevertheless, these findings are in opposition to the older average ages seen in studies carried out in Maharashtra (71.358 ± 6.481 years), the USA (61.01 ± 18.01 years), and Europe (71.31 ± 12.71 years).

The age disparity can be partially attributed to the fact that the Indian population experiences the onset of some heart failure-related illnesses, such as peripartum cardiomyopathy and rheumatic heart disease, at an earlier stage. [26] The study found an association between chronic heart failure and cardiorenal syndrome (CRS) in individuals over the age of 40 who were classified as NYHA class IV. McAliter et al. discovered that within their group, 39% of individuals diagnosed with heart failure symptoms in NYHA class IV and 31% of participants in NYHA class III exhibited a significant level of kidney dysfunction. [13] This study found a significantly higher death rate of 58.5% among individuals with CRS compared to the rates reported in prior investigations. [17] The clinical trial conducted by HR Shah et al. in the field of Cardiorenal research demonstrated an overall death rate of 16%. [4]

The majority of patients in our study had severe cardiac insufficiency, which might explain the higher fatality rates seen in earlier studies. Patients diagnosed with CRS experienced a notably extended duration of hospitalisation (10.422 ± 3.705 days) in comparison to individuals without CRS (8.262 ± 9.553 days, p value-0.00011). A study done in the United States revealed that elderly persons (aged 65 and above) with heart failure and acute renal impairment experienced a 2% higher death

rate and a threefold increase in their hospital stay duration. However, a study done in Nigeria on the worsening of kidney dysfunction in patients with heart failure revealed no significant difference in the duration of hospitalisation between persons with increased kidney impairment and those without. [8] This investigation discovered two precise markers of mortality: a blood urea level exceeding 120 mg/dl and a serum creatinine concentration of 1.9 mg/dl or above. Studies have demonstrated that markers of kidney dysfunction are more accurate predictors of mortality in individuals with chronic renal insufficiency (CRS) compared to indicators of left ventricular dysfunction (left ventricular ejection fraction [LVEF] and New York Heart Association [NYHA] classification). [11-18] Researchers HR Shah et al. identified a robust association between blood creatinine levels and death in persons diagnosed with heart failure. [4] The results of a Prospective Trial of Intravenous Milrinone for Exacerbation of Chronic Heart Failure study revealed that increased levels of serum creatinine (SCr) and urea were identified as important and independent indicators of death or re-hospitalization. [27] After adjusting for confounding factors, a study investigating 1004 consecutive patients with heart failure who were treated at 11 different hospitals found that patients with deteriorating renal function had a 7.5 times higher chance of death during their hospital stay. [28]

Conclusion

Patients with heart failure exhibited a significant prevalence of cardiorenal syndrome (CRS). Independent predictors of CRS were found to be age over 40 years old and NYHA class IV. Individuals with CRS had significantly prolonged hospital stays compared to individuals without CRS. Within the context of medical facilities, individuals with CRS experience a significantly elevated mortality rate. Renal function was assessed by measuring serum creatinine (SCr) levels, specifically those over 1.91 mg/dl, and urea levels larger than 120 mg/dl. These measurements were identified as indicators of mortality. Some patients faced challenges in identifying the major organ, either the heart or the kidneys, that was experiencing failure. This uncertainty may have influenced the categorization of CRS into distinct groups. The incidence of CRS may have been influenced by the exclusion of specific cohorts of heart failure patients, particularly those who received care at outpatient clinics.

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